

Kinetics and Mechanism of Iodination of Disubstituted-phenols in Aqueous Acetic Acid

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Kinetics of iodination of 2,4-dinitro-, 2,4-dichloro- and 2,4-dibromophenols and 5-sulpho- and 5-chlorosalicylic acids by iodine monochloride in (70 : 30%, v/v) acetic acid and water mixture medium, have been studied. The overall order is two in all the three disubstituted-phenols. The individual order with respect to the substrate is one and that with respect to ICl is also one. The effect of solvent has been studied and kinetic parameters have been calculated. The effect of perchloric acid on the reaction rate of 5-chlorosalicylic acid has also been examined. The tentative reaction mechanism for these reactions have been proposed.

The kinetics of iodination of aromatic compounds have been extensively investigated¹, only a few attempts seems to have been made to elucidate the structure and reactivity in the iodination of phenol and substituted-phenols². Hence the present investigation has been undertaken with a view to identify the overall order and individual orders and kinetic parameters of disubstituted-phenols.

Results and Discussion

The overall order determined by fractional life method is found two (Table 1) in all the disubstituted-phenols. The individual orders determined by initial rate method are found to be one with respect to substrate and one with respect to ICl (Table 2). Similar results are also observed in case of iodination of aniline³ and anisole⁴ in aqueous acetic acid by iodine monochloride.

The effect of temperature on the rate constant is established (using pseudo-first order formula) using the mixture of phenol (0.02 M) and ICl (0.002 M) in aqueous acetic acid over the temperature range 20–40°. The rate constant for the reaction of different temperatures are plotted against 1/T and the activation energy, enthalpy change, free energy and entropy change have been calculated (Table 3).

The effect of solvent on the rate constant of 2,4-dinitrophenol-ICl reaction is studied. The rate constant is determined graphically and the pseudo-first order reaction constant of iodination of 2,4-dinitrophenol by ICl is calculated. The results show that the dielectric constant of solvent and the rate of reaction are directly proportional to each other (Table 4).

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF OVERALL ORDER IN ACOH-H₂O MEDIUM (70 : 30%, v/v) BY FRACTIONAL LIFE METHOD AT 30°
[NaClO₄]=0.002 M, [NaCl]=0.002 M, [HClO₄]=0.001 M

[ICl] mol dm ⁻³		t ₂	Time s	Overall order				
C ₂	C ₁			t ₁	2,4-dim-nitro phenol	5-sulpho-salicylic acid	5-chloro salicylic acid	2,4-dichloro phenol
0.002	0.001	150	360	2.2	—	—	—	—
0.002	0.001	420	900	2.0	—	—	—	—
0.001	0.0005	360	810	2.1	—	—	—	—
0.001	0.0005	900	2 100	2.2	—	—	—	—
0.002	0.001	60	120	—	2.0	—	—	—
0.002	0.001	120	264	—	2.1	—	—	—
0.001	0.0005	120	264	—	2.1	—	—	—
0.001	0.0005	264	504	—	1.9	—	—	—
0.002	0.001	96	192	—	—	2.0	—	—
0.002	0.001	168	336	—	—	2.0	—	—
0.001	0.0005	192	360	—	—	1.9	—	—
0.001	0.0005	336	624	—	—	1.9	—	—
0.002	0.001	6.0	13.5	—	—	—	2.0	—
0.002	0.001	15.0	28.5	—	—	—	1.9	—
0.001	0.0005	13.5	27.0	—	—	—	2.0	—
0.001	0.0005	28.5	54.0	—	—	—	1.9	—
0.002	0.001	24.0	60.0	—	—	—	—	2.3
0.002	0.001	48.0	108.0	—	—	—	—	2.1
0.001	0.0005	60.0	132.0	—	—	—	—	2.1
0.001	0.0005	108.0	228.0	—	—	—	—	2.0

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TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF INDIVIDUAL ORDERS BY INITIAL RATE METHOD IN AcOH-H₂O MEDIUM (70 : 30%, v/v) AT 30°
[HClO₄]=0.091 M, [NaClO₄]=0.002 M, [NaCl]=0.002 M

Substrate	Phenol	ICl
2,4-Dinitrophenol	1.2	1.1
5-Sulphosalicylic acid	1.1	1.0
5-Chlorosalicylic acid	1.2	1.1
2,4-Dichlorophenol	1.1	1.0
2,4-Dibromophenol	1.0	1.2

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

[Substrate]=0.02 M, [ICl]=0.002 M, [NaClO₄]=0.002 M,
[NaCl]=0.002 M, [HClO₄]=0.001 M, Temp =30°

Substrate	10 ⁴ × k ₁ s ⁻¹	E _a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	-ΔS [‡] JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔF [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹
2,4-Dinitrophenol	5.11	54.7	52.1	135.9	93.3
5-Sulphosalicylic acid	8.34	27.3	24.8	222.2	92.1
5-Chlorosalicylic acid	9.13	25.5	23.0	227.4	91.9
2,4-Dichlorophenol	17.27	22.5	19.9	232.0	92.5
2,4-Dibromophenol	23.03	21.2	18.7	233.8	89.5

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF SOLVENT ON THE RATE OF IODINATION OF 2,4-DINITROPHENOL

[Substrate]=0.02 M, [ICl]=0.002 M, [NaClO₄]=0.002 M,
[NaCl]=0.002 M, [HClO₄]=0.001 M

Solvent AcOH : H ₂ O (%v,v)	Dielectric constant at 25°	10 ⁴ k ₁ (s ⁻¹)
95 : 5	11.54	1.72
90 : 10	18.20	2.13
85 : 15	28.00	2.74
80 : 20	51.00	3.19

The effect of perchloric acid on the reaction rate of 5-chlorosalicylic acid is also investigated (Table 5). It was found that the influence of varying [H⁺] is negligible at the lower concentration of the acid (0.0025 M), but at higher acid concentration (0.025 M) there is much enhancement in the rate of reaction. The linear plots of log k₁ versus log [H⁺] show that there is a participation of acid [H⁺] in the reaction. This indicates non-participation of acid at lower concentrations and the participation of acid in the rate-determining step at higher concentrations, leading to the dependence of reaction on [H⁺]

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF HClO₄ ON THE REACTION RATE OF 5-CHLOROSALICYLIC ACID

Solvent : AcOH : H₂O (70 : 30%, v/v), [substrate]=0.02 M,
[ICl]=0.002 M, [NaClO₄]=0.002 M, [NaCl]=0.002 M,
Temp. 30°

10 ³ [HClO ₄] M	10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹
2.5	21.3
5.0	22.1
10.0	23.0
25.0	28.7
50.0	46.0
75.0	102.3
100.0	115.1
125.0	117.1

The iodination of disubstituted-phenols in the aqueous acetic acid is of second order. The observed experimental overall order for disubstituted-phenols can be explained by assuming the iodination as the second order process. The general mechanism for second order process is given as

At lower [H⁺] than 0.01 M :

The rate law can be given as

$$-\frac{d[\text{ICl}]}{dt} = k_2 [\text{phenol}] [\text{ICl}]$$

As the concentration of HClO₄ increases, the rate increases. Hence the reaction mechanism is as follows :

At higher [H⁺] than 0.01 M :

Substituent effect : The rate of iodination of various phenols on comparison reveals that the reactivity of different disubstituted-phenols are in the order ; 2,4-dibromophenol > 2,4-dichlorophenol > 5-chlorosalicylic acid > 5-sulphosalicylic acid > 2,4-dinitrophenol. This clearly shows that electron-releasing groups enhance the reaction rate and electron-withdrawing ones retard the rate as has been observed for other electrophilic substitution reactions. The ΔH[‡] and ΔS[‡] values (Table 3) are in good agreement with those of the other

electrophilic substitution reactions⁵. The relatively small positive values of ΔH^\ddagger and large negative values of ΔS^\ddagger show that the reaction passes through highly organised rate-determining transition states in which bond formations are well advanced. Large $-\Delta S^\ddagger$ values also indicates the formation of an intermediate complex in the rate-determining step⁶.

Experimental

The preparation of pure anhydrous acetic acid (f.p. 16.3°) was prepared by the reported method⁷. All the substrate viz. 2,4-Dinitro-, 2,4-dichloro- and 2,4-dibromophenols and 5-sulpho- and 5-chlorosalicylic acids (Fluka or Sigma) were used. The iodine monochloride (Merck, A.R.) were used after dilution. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Kinetic measurements: The reaction was studied by keeping the concentration of phenol at 0.02 *M* and ICl at 0.002 *M* in the presence of perchloric acid (0.001 *M*), sodium perchlorate (0.002 *M*) and sodium chloride (0.002 *M*), in order to prevent the rapid hydrolysis of ICl and minimise the effect of the small amount of Cl⁻ ion formed during substitution.

The concentration of iodine monochloride was determined iodometrically as a function of time. The 'batch method' was adopted⁸ since the reaction

is faster. In this method the ICl and phenol mixture dissolved in aqueous acetic acid (70 : 30%, v/v) (5ml each) were placed in a thermostatic bath at the required temperature. The phenol solution was quickly added to it and the mixture was allowed to react for a specific time. The reaction was arrested by quick addition of potassium iodide (10%, 5 ml), and the liberated iodine was titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate.

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